

Toward a satellite mission to determine the source of the Cosmic Microwave Background – a scientific-philosophical risk analysis

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“A satellite has no conscience.” — Edward R. Murrow

Abstract

The Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) is generally assumed to have a cosmic origin. This assumption has been put into question around the beginning of this century by Pierre-Marie Robitaille, who attributes the CMB monopole signal instead to the oceans of the Earth. Despite his various attempts to reach out to the astrophysics community about this matter, an active dialogue on it is still missing in academia. To break through this impasse, Jim Keller recently initiated a collaboration with a group of individuals with the aim to experimentally test Robitaille’s theories by means of different satellites. In this white paper, I argue why the determination of the CMB monopole’s origin deserves special attention amongst these envisioned satellite missions. Subsequently, the white paper focuses on the risk that such a satellite mission might not be taken seriously by the scientific community, even if its execution and outcome is successful. This risk is illustrated by the public reception – or better the lack thereof – of Paris Herouni’s measurements that suggest the absence of the CMB monopole at the location of his ROT-54/2.6 antenna. Likewise, various defense mechanisms from conventionalists may be expected to discredit the satellite mission, in an attempt to protect the standard cosmological model from any harm. In order to deal with this countermovement in a structured manner, I propose classifying the defense mechanisms into six categories. Because each of them forms a significant risk to the future public reception of the satellite project, I subsequently suggest several strategies to prevent and mitigate them. Finally, I discuss how ground-based experiments form a complementary approach to investigate the CMB monopole origin. The scientific-philosophical risk classification and mitigation methodology proposed in this white paper is also applicable to other experimental work challenging the scientific consensus, making it relevant to non-standard science in general.

Keywords: non-standard astrophysics, non-standard cosmology, crisis in cosmology, blackbody radiation, radio-optical telescope, satellite dish, horn antenna, bolometer, philosophy of misunderstanding, reproducibility crisis, Open Science, Semmelweis reflex.

Highlights:

- Jim Keller has initiated discussions on the feasibility of private satellite missions to experimentally test Pierre-Marie Robitaille's theories.
- A satellite mission indicating an Earthly source of the CMB monopole is expected to most easily overturn the consensus in astrophysics among all envisioned satellite experiments.
- The limited public criticism on Herouni's empirical refutation of the Big Bang theory reveals several risks for experiments challenging the scientific consensus.
- Six categories of risks and their solutions are proposed for experiments challenging the scientific consensus, regarding the anticipated defense mechanisms by conventionalists.
- Accordingly, recommendations are given to minimize these risks for the envisioned satellite mission, as well as complementary ground-based experiments studying the CMB origin.

1. The quest to test the Robitaillean paradigm

1.1. *The Banger satellite – A new hope*

As announced by Pierre-Marie Robitaille in his most recent Sky Scholar videos [1, 2], Jim Keller has invited a group of individuals to San Francisco in January 2026, to discuss launching private satellites into space with the purpose to test a range of ideas, including some related to the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) and the Sun. Even though the videos do not clearly specify which ideas are considered, it will be no surprise that these involve Robitaille's work on the CMB (see e.g. [3–13]) and his liquid solar model (see e.g. [14]). In their tetralogue with Michael Shilo DeLay and Anastasia Bendebury on the DemystifySci Podcast [15], Keller already suggested sending a satellite to the Sun to test its liquid nature, emphasizing the relatively low costs of such endeavor. Clearly, he was not kidding, evidenced by his recent initiative to convert these words into a dedicated first meeting.

Even though I was not physically present at this event, I was fortunate to be included in two of the brainstorming sessions on separate days through hybrid Zoom video calls. Note that the project currently still resides in an exploratory phase, in which the focus lies on a feasibility study of the envisioned satellites relative to the available budget and ambitions. I will therefore refrain myself for now from commenting on the proposed ideas as they ripen, because this is often counterproductive too early in the brainstorming process. Instead, with the underlying document, I intend to provide my personal perspective on the initiative in general at this early stage, or on any future satellite mission aiming to test Robitaille's theories.

Robitaille's work challenges various aspects of the current scientific consensus, ranging from the standard solar model and the standard cosmological model to the very foundations of physics as taught in conventional curricula. Empirically testing his theories can therefore be considered equal to experimentally challenging the scientific consensus. With the experiment at the center of scientific quality control, this is a clear sign of proper science. Still, many of Robitaille's opponents may find this lack of faith in the consensus disturbing. To those opponents who do, I would like to emphasize that science should not be conducted based on faith. I am, however, aware that this mere reminder will not suffice to overcome the ever lurking criticism from followers of the faith often wrongly referred to as science. Dogmatic thinking and subtle variations of it are, unfortunately, prevalent in academia nowadays.

As such, Keller's satellite project does not only face technological challenges, but also scientific-philosophical ones. In both dimensions, each corresponding satellite mission can be categorized as a high-risk/high-gain undertaking. In the present white paper, I will focus on the latter dimension. As I will argue further below, a successful experiment does not guarantee a high convincingness or impact in the scientific community. Keller and his co-workers are therefore advised to take these risks into consideration in their preparation of the experiments. Each satellite mission accordingly obtains a double aim, i.e. to result into a conclusive answer on the targeted research question, as well as to make a proportional impact in the academic discussion. The latter requires a careful navigation through all of the defense mechanisms of academia that will be encountered along the way.

In Section 2.1, I will explain why a satellite mission to determine the source of the CMB forms my preferred strategy to break the impasse we face today in cosmology and science as a whole. As a side note, Keller and his team have already tentatively baptized this satellite with the appropriate name *Bang*. Still, rebellious as I am, I will refer to it below as the *Banger satellite*, for the sake of contrarianism. The need for a scientific-philosophical risk analysis for the corresponding satellite mission will be dealt with in Section 2, where Section 2.1 provides an overview of what we can learn from Paris Herouni's antenna research for this purpose. In Section 2.2, I subsequently translate the obtained insights to the Banger satellite case and contrarian experiments in general, by predicting the various defense mechanisms that the standard scientific community might employ against it. Section 3 lays out several recommendations to mitigate these risks, with Section 3.1 fully devoted to the envisioned Banger satellite mission. Finally, I discuss in Section 3.2 how ground-based experiments with a similar budget can further aid in answering the research question.

1.2. A satellite angling for truth and accountability – Empiricism strikes back

Robitaille's work on the CMB and the liquid solar model is multifaceted, providing several avenues for testing and experimental substantiation. For this reason, it may be hard to choose which of these avenues to take first. In order to facilitate this choice, let's start with why it is useful to experimentally test Robitaille's theory on the CMB and his liquid solar model in the first place.

For more than a quarter of a century, Robitaille has tried to advertise his work to the astrophysical community, to a wider audience of physicists and beyond, by means of scientific papers [3–14], conference talks [16–21], YouTube videos [22–32], interviews and podcasts [15, 33–39], email communication and even a New York Times ad [40]. Despite these wide-ranging efforts, his message remained vastly ignored by the scientific community. In as far as scientists provided feedback on his work, it was, with few exceptions, dismissive, superficial and through informal channels. This was not due to a lack of scientific rigor, novelty or potential impact of Robitaille's theory and arguments. Rather, this can be attributed to the lack of incentives in academia and beyond to explore alternative perspectives opposing the scientific consensus, in combination with the conservative bias in the contemporary peer review culture. These two obstacles are detrimental to the academic quest for efficient scientific progress. Because they are of a structural nature, they will likely require a fully-fledged scientific revolution to be eliminated. While Robitaille's work may very well hold the key to such scientific revolution, this key will need to overcome the two obstacles to enter the academic dialogue before any change will occur.

Proponents of Robitaille's work have therefore two choices on how to deal with this catch-22: (i) either to patiently wait until the scientific revolution unfolds on its own, (ii) or to find a suitable key to unlock the academic dialogue in order to speed up the process. Obviously, the latter option is not without

challenges. First of all, a feasible key needs to be identified within Robitaille's multitude of arguments. Secondly, it needs to pass the defensive barriers of academia, so Robitaille's message no longer remains ignored. During the past five years that I have studied Robitaille's work, I have identified a few of such candidate keys, and tentatively ranked them in order of likeliness to be taken seriously by the scientific community and trigger a scientific revolution. The one that came out on top far beyond the others is what I consider the core hypothesis of Robitaille's message with regard to the CMB:

The monopole of the CMB originates from Earth.

The reasons why it came out on top can be summarized as follows:

- This hypothesis is experimentally testable. This is important, because opponents of a theory are less likely to be convinced by theoretical arguments than by experimental ones.
- If it turns out to be true, the main foundation of the Big Bang theory and the standard cosmological model (Λ CDM) falls away, as I explained in more detail in my DemystiCon 2025 presentation about the CMB [41]. Without this foundation, there is no reason anymore to favor the Big Bang theory over any of its alternatives (see also [42, 43]).
- The Big Bang theory has a special place in science. It is one of the most famous scientific theories, even among the general population, giving it a strong symbolic status. From a sociological point of view, disproving the Big Bang theory may therefore be considered more consequential than disproving the standard solar model or discarding Kirchhoff's universality law of thermal radiation.
- It is simple, singular and rather easy to grasp. By focusing on this hypothesis and this hypothesis alone, many distracting counterarguments related to other aspects of Robitaille's work can be moved to a secondary discussion, in line with the takeaway message from my DemystiCon 2025 presentation [41].
- The hypothesis has already found experimental support in Paris Herouni's observations with his radio-optical telescope [44, 45] (see Section 2.1 for an in-depth discussion).

Note that each of these reasons directly relates to either the hypothesis' convincingness or impact as a counterargument against the Big Bang theory. In this way, they partly address the two aforementioned obstacles. Namely, the more convincing a counterargument appears, the more likely it will enter the broader scientific dialogue. Additionally, the higher its perceived impact, the harder it will be for Big Bang theory proponents to dismiss it as unimportant and not worthy of their time.

Even though Robitaille pointed out many other weaknesses in the standard models and scientific consensus, I do not estimate them to be as impactful and convincing to his opponents as his core hypothesis with regard to the CMB. His counterarguments against Kirchhoff's universality law of thermal radiation, for instance, are inevitably more abstract, because Kirchhoff's law itself is more abstract. The excuse that it would correspond to an approximation of an ideal seems, sadly, sufficient to deter attention away from it, notwithstanding how useless the approximation is. As such, we may expect the standard scientific community to mostly disregard this issue, despite its vast consequences, as evidenced by the relatively slowly growing number of citations of Robitaille's paper on the topic published in the reputable journal *IEEE transactions on plasma science* [46]. His counterarguments against the standard solar model, on the other hand, need to somehow circumvent the model's complexity. That is, if a single counterargument puts one aspect of the model into question, standard astrophysicists may solve this by means of an additional ad hoc auxiliary hypothesis to save the rest of the model. This severely complicates the discussion, giving the standard model's proponents a lot of room to manoeuvre. A similar strategy can be taken relative to Robitaille's scepticism about the CMB

anisotropy maps, because they contain many free parameters. With this, I do not mean to claim that these arguments are weak or less worthy of consideration overall. Instead, I estimate their potential to convince the opposing party to be relatively low. Therefore, I will only focus on the experimental identification of the source of the CMB monopole in the remainder of the present document.

In conclusion, if the purpose is to convince the broader scientific community about the importance of Robitaille's work, the disputed origin of the CMB monopole seems the most recommended place to start. If experiments decisively point toward an Earthly origin, a strong argument is formed in favor of the Robitaillean paradigm that the standard scientific community will find hard to ignore. Obviously, a satellite mission dedicated to this purpose will attract additional attention to the findings, increasing the chance that standard astrophysicists finally start paying attention to the issues in their standard models as pointed out by Robitaille. However, in the following Section 2, I will argue that even a satellite mission indicating an Earthly origin of the CMB monopole may not be sufficient to convince the wider scientific community. Correspondingly, I will provide recommendations on how to avoid this risk in Section 3.

2. The need for a scientific-philosophical risk analysis

2.1. Learning from the past – Return of Herouni

Robitaille's core hypothesis with regard to the CMB has already been substantiated by means of Herouni's ROT-54/2.6 antenna, which measured the absence of the monopole signal in a dry region of Armenia under dry weather conditions [44, 45]. This experimental finding aligns with Robitaille's proposal that the monopole signal originates from the oceans, while it contradicts the Big Bang theory. Yet, it was met with a deafening radio silence from the astrophysics community, with very few exceptions. For example, Robitaille mentions the following in his video on Herouni's antenna [22]:

Herouni should have had a total signal of about 6K, with some signal coming from the cosmos, but the signal was just not there. So, he sent his data to ten of the world's top laboratories and asked them to highlight potential errors in his measurements. None of them replied. Of course, there was no error. Herouni was an expert in radio engineering. He knew how to measure antenna noise. Professor Herouni paused for a period of ten years before publishing his data, waiting for any answer. His first publication was in a Greek journal, as you can see here [44].

Herouni's work displays at least two interesting parallels with an envisioned satellite mission that confirms an Earthly origin of the CMB monopole:

- both experimental studies would disprove the Big Bang theory, with revolutionary consequences, and
- both studies use highly specialised, eye-catching and relatively expensive devices and techniques in a popular scientific domain.

For Herouni's case, this corresponds to the curious juxtaposition of an explicitly consequential scientific investigation that has been ignored despite its high attention-grabbing potential. It demonstrates that the importance of scientific results does not guarantee that awareness of these results will spread through the broader scientific community or even that they will be taken seriously by academia. Therefore, scientists willing to send a satellite into space to identify the CMB monopole's true origin are strongly advised to understand this juxtaposition, so they can prevent it from happening as well to their research.

In the present Section 2.1, I will accordingly explore what can be learned from the current situation with Herouni's findings, in order to apply the obtained insights in later sections.

On Google Scholar, Herouni's paper from 2007 on the absence of the CMB monopole signal in his measurements is currently indexed with only two citations, one of which by his successors working on the antenna, which is currently out of service [47], and another of which by Yuri Vladimirovich Gusev, acknowledging the uncertain observational foundation of the currently dominant cosmological model [48]. An additional search on Google Scholar combining the keyword "Big Bang" with "Herouni" provides one more document by Shifu R. Careaga referring to the article, although without any further discussion of the reference [49]. The same author, however, devoted another document not indexed by Google Scholar to the reviewing of Herouni's 2007 paper by means of a combination of large language models, resulting in a favorable evaluation [50]. Hence, counterarguments or criticism against Herouni's conclusion on the CMB seem absent in the scientific literature indexed by Google Scholar. Likewise, I have not found any attempts to counter Herouni's interpretation among the publically available criticism on Robitaille's work on the CMB by his opponents.

However, vague criticism can be found in the history of Paris Herouni's Wikipedia page. On September 12th 2022, an anonymous user slandered the scientist with two sequential edits. In the first edit, the user depicted Herouni as a pseudoscientist, commenting [51]:

Pseudoscientist best describes the claims that this scientist made.

The revision was quickly undone by the user ThatSpiderByte due to the lack of references to the claim. In the second edit of the anonymous user, the following text was added to the page, which remained visible until July 27th 2023 [52]:

The so-called first Radio-Optical Telescope, operated under the supervision of Herouni, measured the Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation as 2.6K which is slightly less than the accepted value of 2.7K. Based on this single measurement, Herouni claimed that " there never was any Big Bang in Universe." [45] This paper entitled 'Measured Parameters of Large Antenna of ROT-54/2.6 Tell about Absence of Big Bang' has only five references, all of which are self-citations.

While open for interpretation, this quote seems to include three criticisms on Herouni's paper:

1. According to this text, the 2.6K noise recorded by the telescope would correspond to the CMB monopole, which is only slightly less than the expected value of 2.7K generally attributed to the CMB in other measurements, and Herouni's conclusion of the absence of a Big Bang would be based on this assessment.
2. This would concern a single measurement, rather than a continuous or repeated measurement.
3. The paper contains five references in its bibliography, all of which are self-citations.

The first criticism is based on a misunderstanding of Herouni's measurement, because the expected recorded signal should have included both the CMB (2.7K) and the self-noise of the telescope (2.6K), thus amounting to 5.3K in total, whereas only 2.6K was measured. The absence of self-noise from the telescope is impossible, so proponents of the Big Bang theory have a very hard – if not impossible – puzzle to solve with this observation. Accordingly, the first criticism can be discarded as incorrect. The user Pablo Mayrgundter detected this error and corrected the Wikipedia text on July 27th 2023 [51, 53].

The second criticism is incorrect as well, although Herouni's publications are not fully explicit about this. His aforementioned paper indeed mentions that the determination of the 2.6K noise corresponds to

recordings taken on the 23rd and 24th of November 1988 around 11pm – 12am. However, the paper also refers to these results as follows [45]:

The result presented on Fig. 3 [of the paper] introduced more in details the process of ROT Antenna Self Noises measurements which were done mainly in 1988 and later. (...) We are keeping the original of these records. In some of them we received $T_{SN} = 2.8K$, which are in the limits of $\pm 10\%$ accuracy [44, 54].

This implies that similar measurements were made on different moments, providing a reproducible result. Correspondingly, an earlier paper of 1999 by Herouni about the self-noise and the absence of the CMB monopole signal mentions a different experiment that provided a slightly different temperature of 2.8K, with the following context [44]:

The ROT Antenna (...) begins operating in 1988 and one of the first measurements were, of course, the self noise ones. The result was indeed impressive even for us (expecting a very low level). It was equal about 3K in waverange of 8mm. Such a result is obtained, of course, not at each day, but in the days with very clean sky and dry air.

As the latter sentence confirms, Herouni noticed a pattern in the occurrence of the low noise level disproving the Big Bang, implying that it was observed on different occasions. Moreover, this pattern corresponded, in his own words, with “days with very clean sky and dry air”. This corresponds to the conditions with minimal atmospheric interference for microwave radiation, as generally recommended for ground-based CMB measurements, in addition to locations at high altitudes.

As should be noted, Herouni’s telescope is located in a dry region, far away from any lakes and oceans. This fully aligns with Robitaille’s theory that the CMB monopole originates from water bodies on Earth, which therefore could be absent in such dry areas under dry weather conditions. In this respect, Robitaille has pointed out on several occasions that water is known to affect CMB measurements, suggesting that it is an effective natural emitter of microwaves [9, 55]. This realization should be alarming to Big Bang proponents, and even more so that Herouni and Robitaille came to their mutually consistent conclusions independently from one another.

In any case, we may also interpret the second criticism in an alternative way, namely that the absence of the CMB monopole has only been observed with Herouni’s antenna, so the measurement has never been independently reproduced. Even so, this should serve as a motivation for the scientific community to reproduce the measurement with other devices or by other researchers, rather than an excuse to dismiss the result.

The third criticism may seem of little value, because the quality of a measurement or the importance of a discovery stands loose from which references are mentioned along its publication. Still, such arguments related to the context rather than the content of a publication form a returning theme in the criticism against work like Herouni’s and Robitaille’s that put the scientific consensus into question. One of the most repeated counterarguments against Robitaille’s work is, for instance, that his papers were mainly published in the alternative scientific journal *Progress in Physics*, rather than a more reputable one indexed in the Web of Science. Even if such arguments may seem irrelevant, the fact that they frequently reoccur in the criticism of Robitaille’s work suggests that they will remain a returning pattern in future discussions as well.

Further criticism on Herouni's work regarding the CMB can be found in Russian sources on the internet. In a Science Mail article of April 3rd, 2025, Irina Bokova wrote the following with respect to the measured absence of the CMB radiation in Herouni's measurements [56]:

По мнению научного сообщества, данные Геруни весьма ограничены и не могут соревноваться с доказательствами международных исследований. Вероятнее всего, желаемой точности 2,6 К в телескопе Геруни создать не получилось из-за уменьшения его диаметра с 200 м до 54. Таким образом, устройство не отличается рекордно низкой шумовой температурой, и оно не способно уловить подобный диапазон.

which can be translated as:

According to the scientific community, Herouni's data are quite limited and cannot compete with the evidence of international studies. Most likely, it was not possible to create the desired accuracy of 2.6 K in the Herouni telescope due to the reduction of its diameter from 200 m to 54. Thus, the device does not have a record low noise temperature, and it is not able to capture such a range.

This citation refers to an article in Russian from 2019 on the website of the Armenian newspaper Golos Armenii [57], presenting a denunciation of Herouni's antenna, also referred to as DAS-50 (ДАС-50) in the article, in the context of the state program dealing with the instrument's possible restoration. The criticism was more specifically given by Akop Arutyunyan and Hrant Khachatryan, two former colleagues of Herouni. Bokova's generalization of the "scientific community" therefore seems to correspond to these two scientists.

Arutyunyan, who worked as the head of the metrology sector in Herouni's institute from 1971 to 1978, claimed in his assessment that the telescope never worked, because the basic principles of antenna technology would have been violated in its design, making the telescope unable to operate in the decimeter and other microwave wavelength range. His translated opinion reads as follows [57]:

The main violations (...) are the bulky metal structures for moving the small mirror. In addition, the supports obscure the central zone of the large mirror and distort the distribution of the electromagnetic field, which creates the main parameter of the antenna: the radiation pattern, on which the rest of the antenna parameters depend: gain, efficiency, width of the main lobe of the DN, etc. The radiation pattern for any antenna must be a constant value, and for the DAS-50 it is variable, depending on the movement of the small mirror. (...) In accordance with the project, DAS-50 was designed to operate in the microwave range. But (...) it cannot work in this wave range, primarily because of reflections from metal structures. In addition, the accuracy of the manufacture of a large mirror should be 1/16 of the wavelength, i.e. about 0.025 mm. Even if we do not take into account rereflections, then when operating in the decimeter wave range (...) the DAS-50 will be equal to about a five-meter spherical antenna of the microwave range, and not to a 50-meter one as in the project.

Khachatryan, a radio engineer who dealt directly with antenna topics in Herouni's institute from 1973 to 1978, added that the following doubts existed during the construction of the telescope [57]:

It was known from the beginning that the use of a fixed spherical main mirror with some of its advantages has serious drawbacks. When designing antenna systems of such designs, it is necessary to find an optimal compromise between the overall dimensions of the antenna system, its effective surface, the field of view and a number of parameters related to the practical

implementation of the design and measuring equipment. During the calculations of the DAS-50, the contractors had doubts that with the chosen configuration (size and relative location of the main and secondary mirrors), the profile of the secondary mirror and the location of its focus theoretically could not provide close to reasonable optimal parameters of the entire system. Some specialists directly involved in the calculations of the various options even believed that it was impossible to calculate a practically workable secondary mirror with the given initial data.

Finally, the article concludes its criticism by pointing out the wide support for the Big Bang theory [57]:

“Especially deeply doubtful are the results allegedly obtained during the first tests in the centimeter range, on the basis of which a sensational statement was made to the whole world about the refutation of the Big Bang Theory. (...) Herouni once stated at a meeting of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Armenia that with his antenna (which, by the way, never worked) he disproved the existence of residual cosmic microwave background radiation. He was not even stopped by the fact that two outstanding American scientists received the Nobel Prize for the detection of the CMB radiation,” the microwave antenna specialist Arutyunyan said with indignation.

In the latter sentence, the verb “возмущается”, interpreted here as “to say with indignation”, is of particular interest within the context of the present scientific-philosophical analysis. Alternative translations are “to be exasperated” and “to be outraged”, each conveying a clearly negative emotional stance on the topic. The interviewed expert Arutyunyan thus expresses his frustration about Herouni’s claim that his antenna disproved the Big Bang theory, despite Pensias’ and Wilson’s Nobel Prize in favor of the theory. He accordingly uses this Nobel Prize as an argument to call Herouni’s measurement of the absence of the CMB especially deeply doubtful. This can be seen as a form of circular reasoning, because experiments are meant to test hypotheses and theories, not the other way around. Moreover, it reveals a bias of Arutyunyan as a reviewing expert. As such, it is very likely that he is sceptical about the antenna’s proper functioning especially due to its contradiction with Pensias’ and Wilson’s Nobel Prize. This could have caused his heavy critique on its technological aspects, or at the very least worsened it. Next to that, he worked in Herouni’s institute, so it cannot be excluded that a personal dispute between him and Herouni might have further colored his evaluation of the telescope.

Khachatryan, in contrast, sounds more objective, even emphasizing the need for an independent group of specialists to make a final decision on the restoration of ROT-54/2.6 in the state program, according to the article. It is doubtful, however, that any group of specialists, even those carefully assembled, can be considered truly independent. Everyone is biased in some way, through education, culture, world view, personal perspective on science and academia, and other environmental and personal factors. Every specialist favoring the Big Bang theory or the scientific consensus in general will automatically be biased towards presuming that something is wrong with Herouni’s antenna, his measurements or his interpretation regarding the CMB. Every expert questioning the Big Bang theory or the scientific consensus will be more inclined to take Herouni’s work on the CMB more seriously. The ideal of an unbiased specialist as someone with the required expertise for a radio-optical telescope evaluation, yet a lack of interest in Herouni’s claims on the CMB is unachievable at best, and impossible if there is any overlap between the two. The most practical resolution, in my understanding, is to compare the different viewpoints, so a balanced risk-versus-reward analysis can be made for the antenna’s restoration.

Ironically, the criticism on the antenna’s technological aspects by Arutyunyan and Khachatryan can be turned into arguments in favor of its restoration, by simply looking at the situation from a different

perspective. Let's imagine for a moment that we are in a future where Robitaille's hypothesis on the origin of the CMB monopole has been proven correct by several independent experiments. Let's further assume for the sake of the thought experiment that Herouni's telescope would have never been restored and that criticism on its technological aspects, such as the one given by like Arutyunyan and Khachatryan, is sufficiently justified to cast doubt over the correct functioning of the unprecedented device. This would lead to a dilemma: either Herouni's unique telescope functioned correctly despite these concerns and he was the first to experimentally disprove the Big Bang theory, or the antenna was dysfunctional and Herouni came to the right conclusion with the wrong methodology by coincidence. Scientists would only be able to speculate about the validity of the experiment. If the telescope got restored instead, further testing and experiments with the device can give full clarity about its capabilities and limits, and confirm the correctness of Herouni's methodology. The restoration has therefore the potential to greatly enhance our understanding of the involved technology, next to all the new insights it may bring about the universe.

In this light, I would like to motivate the proponents of Robitaille's hypothesis and Herouni's work to formulate an official rebuttal to the aforementioned criticism on the ROT-54/2.6. The arguments put forward by Arutyunyan and Khachatryan deserve a public counterstatement, in order to maintain a healthy dialogue. The dialogue can only be kept healthy by elevated efforts from Herouni's proponents, as long as they remain a minority. Are Arutyunyan's and Khachatryan's concerns about the antenna's technological features justified? If not, why not? If they are, can counterarguments be formulated showing that the antenna design still works or still may work despite them? In other words, can certainty be given based on the antenna design that it worked or did not work and how well it worked, or is the only way to know whether it works or how well it works by restoring it and testing it further? Because the present white paper only concerns itself with the scientific-philosophical analysis, a deep dive into the technological details lies outside its scope.

Still, from a more general perspective, I would like to point out a contradiction in the criticism. If the ROT-54/2.6 was truly dysfunctional or unreliable, how was it possible for the telescope to accidentally record the explosion of a red giant in the Gemini constellation [47, 58]? The associated radio flare was measured at a frequency of 1.5 GHz, i.e. a wavelength of 20 cm, well within the decimeter range in which the antenna is deemed unable to operate according to Arutyunyan. It seems that this discovery and Arutyunyan's conclusion of a dysfunctional antenna cannot both be true. Next to that, it needs to be mentioned that other experts, such as Kees van 't Klooster, a former antenna specialist from the European Space Agency, as well as the international Advisory Group of the European VLBI Network, recognize the potential of the ROT-54/2.6 antenna as a functional single dish telescope [59, 60]. Having a more public and international dialogue about these different opinions will likely work in favor of the antenna restoration.

The lack of further public criticism on Herouni's claim of disproof of the Big Bang theory, at least to the best of my knowledge, may be due to several reasons. For starters, most proponents of the Big Bang theory are likely unaware of Herouni's findings, because his few publications on the topic have been buried in the archives of internationally poorly known scientific journals and its appearance in the media has only been occasional (see e.g. [61]). Still, it is unlikely that no other proponents of the Big Bang have encountered Herouni's claims on its disproof, either through the occasional media attention or through Robitaille's work. However, one can only speculate how those who are aware of it look at the evidence. Perhaps, some of them simply brush it away with the prejudice that it would not be worthy of consideration. Others may look at it as a curiosity for which they do not have the expertise to re-evaluate it or even understand its importance. For those who have the expertise, partially or fully, many other reasons can be thought of, such as their conservative bias, a lack of incentives or time to study Herouni's

papers in more detail or to discuss it further in the public domain, a misinterpretation of the study, an underestimation of its importance, or specific criticism on the methodology, similar to the one discussed above. We recognize once more the same two obstacles mentioned in Section 2.1 for Robitaille’s work:

1. There are currently no incentives in academia to actively detect and explore alternative perspectives opposing the scientific consensus.
2. The contemporary peer review culture is characterized by a conservative bias, causing the broader scientific community to systematically protect and defend the scientific consensus.

Correspondingly, we should not expect an automatic uptake of contrarian information into the academic conversation. Instead, we may even expect the scientific community to actively block contrarian interpretations, with various counterarguments or avoidance of the discussion overall.

In summary, while Herouni’s findings regarding the CMB may be considered a huge threat to the Big Bang theory and the entire standard cosmological model, they had no perceivable effect for more than two and a half decennia on cosmology in practice. Contrarians questioning the standard CMB interpretation are urged to learn from this situation. As the saying goes, fool me once, shame on you; fool me twice, shame on me. Even if a future satellite mission will be successful in indicating or identifying an Earthly origin of the CMB monopole, there will be no guarantee that its findings will efficiently be disseminated throughout academia, nor that the broader scientific community will easily get convinced by them. In contrast, it seems more likely that the cosmological community will try to find arguments to dismiss the results, or reinterpret them in a way that saves the Big Bang theory, similar to the aforementioned criticism on Herouni’s antenna. By anticipating these risks, preventive steps can be taken in the design of the satellite and its mission, in order to leave less room for counterarguments and criticism from Big Bang proponents afterwards. In the next Section 2.2, I will propose a methodology for such a scientific-philosophical risk analysis.

2.2. Predicting the future backlash – The pseudophilosophy menace

A fully-fledged risk analysis takes into account both the possible risks and their probabilities. For the present scientific-philosophical risk analysis, I intend to focus, however, on the worst-case scenario, in which all possible risks would play out in terms of backlash from the scientific community. My motivation for this choice is partly based on my personal experience and observations with regard to reactions on Robitaille’s work in astrophysics and the foundations of physics, as well as other contrarian ideas that challenge the scientific consensus. Several examples of such confrontations can be found in videos on the DemystifySci Podcast YouTube channel (see e.g. [62, 63]), in the Q&A section of some recorded presentations (see e.g. [41]), and in the comment section of various videos dealing with this or related topics (see e.g. [64]). As a detailed discussion of these reactions lies outside the scope of the present document, I will limit my assessment to a simple yet helpful rule of thumb, which even has the potential to become a new law of nature:

Where a spark of doubt strikes the dogmatic dark, those who dwell in the shadows shall spare no effort to quench its light.

Applied to the current state-of-affairs in science, this can be reformulated as:

When the scientific consensus is challenged by a certain argument, proponents of the scientific consensus will try every trick in the book to counter or discredit that argument.

This prevalent attitude in academia underlies the conservative bias of the formal peer review process. Reversely, the formal peer review process reinforces this attitude. Accepting this situation as the unavoidable fate of the contrarian scientist, preparing for it becomes a recommended strategy, especially if one wants to achieve the biggest impact with a single satellite mission.

As should be noted, this insight invites us to a role playing game, where we take up the roles of both the contrarian and the conventionalist. These two characters have partly different aims, which go beyond challenging and defending the scientific consensus. That is, the contrarian aims to change the status quo by overturning the existing consensus indefinitely. To the conventionalist, this is perceived as an existential threat, which therefore motivates him to not only counter the attack, but also to prevent the consensus from being attacked in the future. From the conventionalist's perspective, the stakes are extremely high, so he will defend the consensus until the bitter end. Even if this seems unwarranted to the contrarian, it is important to keep in mind that the conventionalist controls the rules of the game.

Here, a distinction needs to be made between epistemic rationality and instrumental rationality. If the discussion was held purely with epistemic rationality, there would not be a difference between the contrarian and the conventionalist, because both would have the same goals. Epistemic rationality would have prevented the current situation from occurring. The need for a satellite mission to unambiguously identify the origin of the CMB monopole would be clear to all parties involved without the need to convince anyone. In that regard, Robitaille and his proponents have the moral high ground, as they have already adopted this perspective. Yet, that is not how cosmology is conducted in practice nowadays. The aforementioned role playing game is inherently subjective. The conventionalist is trained and incentivized to use instrumental rationality to shoot down any argument challenging the consensus, whereas the contrarian is forced to play the game according to the rules defined by the conventionalist. The contrarian is thus strongly advised to gain a sufficient insight into the perspective of the conventionalist, in order to beat him at his own game. If the conventionalist cannot be beaten with his own logic, change is unlikely to happen.

This interaction can therefore be understood as a role playing game with a potential winner and a potential loser. The roles are, however, severely asymmetric. The contrarian can only win by successfully overturning the consensus, which requires a flawless argument. For the conventionalist, on the other hand, it suffices to poke a single hole in the argument with any convincing counterargument to have it effectively neutralized. Admittedly, causing a higher level of doubt about the existing consensus can serve as a loser trophy to the contrarian, but I will assume in the following that the purpose is to fully overturn the consensus with a single satellite mission, or as few missions as possible.

The conventionalist can choose between various defense strategies to counter the contrarian's attack. A first low-effort option is to simply ignore the attack, which has been proven effective in the past, as we know from Herouni's case. Another option is to take a protective stance while avoiding a direct confrontation, for instance, by praising the apparent resistance of the Big Bang theory against prior challenges and dismissing the new one as just more of the same. A more direct approach could consist in falsely reassuring that the origin of the CMB monopole would already have been determined as being from outer space, in trying to reject the research question. As a fourth method, the conventionalist might even attempt to use a misunderstanding of the challenge to dismiss it, in line with the common misinterpretations of Robitaille's work discussed in my presentation on the CMB at DemystiCon 2025 [41]. Note that most of such strategies can be categorized as intentional or unintentional distractions from the confrontation.

Alternatively, the conventionalist can decide to acknowledge the assault on the Big Bang theory, but try to prove it invalid by pointing out its weaknesses or mistakes. For this purpose, there are, roughly speaking, three potential points of counterattack. Firstly and most importantly, one weakness in the methodology can be sufficient to dismiss the challenge. For the satellite, this concerns the device, the way in which it is used, and how any recorded data is processed. Secondly, the conventionalist may be inclined to question the validity of the research results even if no clear mistakes can be found in the methodology. For example, incomplete information in the report or unknown or uncontrolled factors can be assumed to have affected the results. Any inexperience of the contrarian with the methodology will also serve as an attractive target for criticism. Next to that, if the experiment has only been performed once, with one instrument or by one team, the conventionalist can use this lack of demonstrated reproducibility to cast doubt about the results. Thirdly, the conventionalist may try to argue that the interpretation of the results is wrong or uncertain. The contrarian is well advised to leave as little room as possible for the interpretation of the results.

In short, a satellite mission identifying an Earthly origin of the CMB monopole will be perceived by the cosmological community as a direct attack on the Big Bang theory and the standard cosmological model. Rather than being welcomed as a captivating finding or a giant leap in scientific progress, such discovery is expected to become a target of heavy criticism due to the strong conservative bias of the current academic culture. Based on previously observed defense mechanisms in the cosmological debate, this criticism can come in the form of distractive and confrontational counterarguments. In order to achieve the strongest impact and the fastest adoption of the envisioned research insights, the Banger satellite team is therefore advised to anticipate the possible counterarguments, so they can be effectively prevented. In Section 3.1, I will provide several recommendations to accomplish this.

3. Recommendations to mitigate the risks

3.1. How to make the satellite a real banger – Attack of the common sense

As we consider a worst-case scenario for the anticipated reaction of the scientific community on the Banger satellite mission, if it indeed points toward an Earthly origin of the CMB monopole, one or more solutions need to be formulated for each of the risks separately. That is, conventionalists will likely be inclined to apply a combination of counterarguments, once they take the threat seriously that the satellite poses to the standard cosmological model. More precisely, based on previous encounters of a similar kind, I anticipate criticism to take the form of several targeted attacks on specific aspects of the satellite mission, followed by praise of the standard cosmological model, the Big Bang theory and prior CMB-related research in favor of the standard paradigm. This seems the classical approach to neutralize a threat to the scientific consensus, because conventionalists prefer to emphasize the strength of the convention over the presence of the threat. In order to return the spotlight to the threat, the contrarians will do well to first counter the praise, followed by addressing any more specific criticism on the satellite.

Table I correspondingly summarizes the main anticipated risks of the satellite mission research with proposed solutions for each. For starters, even if a satellite mission of this calibre may seem hard to ignore, the risk that the scientific community might avoid a conversation about it should not be underestimated. If it can happen to Herouni's research with his multi-million-dollar antenna, it can certainly also happen to a satellite mission with a much lower estimated cost. This risk can be mitigated in several ways, which will vary in effectivity. In my opinion, the most recommended approach is to publish the research in a high impact factor journal. Despite the strong conservative bias of the formal peer review process, this should be much more straightforward for experimental research challenging

the consensus than for nonstandard scientific theoretical work. Once published, the very fact that the research passed the peer review process will serve as an easy and quick argument in further communication that it should not be ignored. Besides this, marketing the research can increase the attention it receives in the mainstream media, which will make it hard for the scientific community to fully ignore it. Directly confronting astrophysicists with the research results is another way to get their reaction. Anyhow, the main aim should be to receive an official reaction on the research from non-anonymous scientists or scientific institutions, to make sure that rebuttal of any criticism is possible.

Table I. Risks, i.e. the anticipated opposing reactions of the scientific community, regarding the convincingness and impact of experimental research that contradicts the scientific consensus, as well as proposed solutions to mitigate these risks.

Risk	Proposed solutions
Research ignored by the scientific community	Publish in a high impact factor journal; market the research; directly confront astrophysicists with the research output.
Distractive criticism and counterarguments	Keep the message focused; avoid multiple key messages; remain vigilant about distractions during dialogue; refocus the conversation; keep the focus on experimental data, rather than theory.
Misinterpretation of the research and false premises	Keep the message focused; screen communication for clarity; remain vigilant about misunderstandings and false premises; use peer reviewed literature to reject or question false premises.
Criticism on the methodology	Use well-known and trusted technologies and methods; adopt historically high-profile methodologies; test and retest instruments; have the instruments and methods audited by independent certified experts.
Criticism on the results and reproducibility	Repeat measurements with the same device and with different devices; have the instruments and measurements audited by independent certified experts; collaborate with trusted parties; follow Open Science practices.
Criticism on the interpretation	Leave no room for alternative interpretations; focus on reproducible patterns, rather than suggestive data; avoid overinterpretation.

When a conversation on the satellite mission is established, the next hurdle to tackle is distractive dialogue. As mentioned in Section 2.2, many defensive counterarguments in favor of the Big Bang theory are distracting from the takeaway message of the satellite mission. These may be considered traps set by the conventionalist – whether intentional or not – for the contrarian. The main risk in this regard is that the contrarian falls in the trap by following the conventionalist’s line of thought, away from the key message. This would give the conventionalist the opportunity to dispute the validity of the research merely based on the apparent decisiveness of previous research or the scientific consensus. To avoid falling in this trap, the contrarian can take both preventive and corrective measures for conversational hygiene. As prevention, the contrarian is advised to keep the message of the satellite research focused. The research namely revolves around a single core hypothesis regarding the Earthly origin of the CMB monopole, so there is no need for any other key messages. When countering criticism on the satellite mission, the focus should remain the same. If conventionalists attempt to shift the focus to another topic, it is up to the contrarian to refocus the conversation as soon as possible.

The latter may sound more straightforward than it is, so I will briefly elaborate on it. Most, if not all, of such distracting counterarguments can be formulated as a separate challenging question to the contrarian: “How can you explain that X, where X contradicts the findings of your satellite mission?” If the contrarian attempts to answer this question, he unintentionally makes it seem as if the conventionalist has a valid point, while this is not necessarily true. The question may namely be ill-posed. This is the case if the proposition X is false, or if there is no contradiction. In that case, rather than answering the question, the contrarian will do well to reveal the ill-posed nature of the question.

Let’s consider a few examples, to make this solution more concrete. The conventionalist may defend the assumed cosmic nature of the CMB monopole with the historical fact that relic radiation from the Big Bang was predicted before the CMB had been measured. In this case, X = “Lemaître predicted relic radiation before the CMB was measured”, which is a true proposition. However, this proposition does not contradict the findings of the satellite mission. It can actually be argued that it further substantiates the wrong attribution of the CMB monopole to a cosmic origin due to the confirmation bias of the later generations of cosmologists.

As a second example, the conventionalist may erroneously claim that the oceans cannot emit blackbody radiation at 2.7K. In this case, X can be formulated as “it is impossible that the oceans emit blackbody radiation at 2.7K”, which is false, in as far as the available evidence can tell us. However, instead of attempting to argue why oceans might emit blackbody radiation at 2.7K in line with Robitaille’s work, a better strategy for the contrarian will be to point out that this is but one of the possible interpretations of the satellite’s results, if it indeed confirms an Earthly origin of the CMB monopole. By refocusing the conversation to the satellite’s findings, i.e. an Earthly origin, without further specifying it as coming from the oceans, the contrarian effectively disarms the conventionalist’s counterargument and avoids getting into the weeds of Robitaille’s theory on thermodynamics. The research question which source on Earth emits the measured signal can then elegantly be shifted aside as a topic for future experimental research that lies outside the scope of the satellite mission, rather than forcing such an overinterpretation of the data. If the conventionalist reinterprets his counterargument as X = “it is impossible that an Earthly source possesses a temperature of 2.7K”, the contrarian can neutralize it by pointing out that this is not a requirement for the satellite mission results to be correct. This temperature may namely be apparent, instead of the actual temperature of the source.

As a side note, this is not to say that an in-depth discussion on these related topics would be unnecessary or uninteresting. Instead, I mean that getting into such details is unnecessary while countering any criticism on the satellite mission results. Such discussion will be more productive after rather than before the experimental results are accepted as valuable. Once more, this should be seen as a strategy in the context of instrumental rationality, instead of epistemic rationality. The main purpose of the Banger satellite mission should be to provide conclusive evidence for the Earthly origin of the CMB monopole, because it will likely be insufficient to provide more detailed information on the origin (even though I will propose below that it may be possible, yet technologically more challenging). At this point in the conversation, I would even argue that it is too preliminary to focus on a possible oceanic origin of the CMB monopole in the context of the satellite mission, because conventionalists can easily invoke several counterarguments that are deemed valid in the standard paradigm, e.g. about the interference of the atmosphere. This would once more distract from the core hypothesis of Robitaille’s message with regard to the CMB as formulated in Section 1.2. By keeping the exact source of the CMB monopole unspecified, other than being Earthly, such counterarguments can be effectively disarmed. Moreover, by avoiding an overinterpretation of the experimental results, the focus is kept on the empirical nature of the satellite mission. This is the aspect on which the conventionalist and the contrarian can most easily find agreement, whereas their perspectives vastly differ on the involved theories.

Once the conversation is refocused on the satellite mission, the next risk to look out for is a misinterpretation of the research. I want to emphasize it here, because misunderstandings of Robitaille's work appear to be prevalent, as discussed in my presentation at DemystiCon 2025 [41]. A part of the solution is identical to the one for distractive criticism: the discussion needs to be kept focused on the key message. As an additional preventive measure, it will be wise to thoroughly screen any official communication about the satellite mission for clarity. Ambiguous or dubious formulations need to be avoided. For instance, a strong emphasis is required on the part of the CMB that is being investigated, because the satellite mission does not concern any measurements of the CMB anisotropy maps. Next to that, in the conversation, the contrarian needs to remain vigilant about possible misunderstandings of the research by conventionalists. A recommended way to do this is by reformulating the criticism by the conventionalists, to ask them whether the reformulation is correct.

As a closely related issue, conventionalists may base their counterarguments on false premises that contradict or misrepresent the peer reviewed literature, without necessarily involving a misinterpretation of the research or claims from the contrarian. Such false premises could emerge, for instance, from misconceptions about conventional theories or reputable historic experiments. This may keep the dialogue in an impasse until the false premises are identified and addressed. Contrarians therefore need to pay attention to hidden misconceptions in the criticism by conventionalists. As should be noted, this implies a possible overlap with distractive counterarguments, because the latter can also be based on false propositions. Still, whether a counterargument needs to be classified as distractive or erroneous largely depends on how important it is with respect to the contrarian's key message. If a discussion on it can be postponed or avoided, it is best treated as distractive by means of a concise response. If, in contrast, it undermines the contrarian's key message, it may require a more elaborate rejoinder. In any case, once a false premise has been detected, the contrarian is advised using the peer reviewed literature to neutralize it. If a brief reference to the literature does not suffice and the counterargument undermines the contrarian's key message, a more in-depth discussion on the false premise should, of course, not be avoided.

A particular false premise to look out for is the denial of the problem that the contrarian tries to solve. For the Banger satellite mission, for example, conventionalists may argue that the CMB monopole would already have been unambiguously proven to originate from outer space. To prevent such erroneous counterargument, the contrarian is prescribed to substantiate the problem statement in the experimental report with sufficient references to the peer reviewed literature. If this still turns out to be ineffective, the exact false premises in the denial by the conventionalist needs to be diagnosed and remediated, before the dialogue can progress toward the next stage.

The next major risk to address concerns the methodology. For a satellite mission using specialized tools and methods, there are many ways to cast doubt on the correct functioning of the instruments and the correct usage of analysis techniques. The most elegant way to tackle this problem consists in using well-known and trusted technologies and methods, preferably standard techniques applied in earlier high-profile research in which the CMB monopole was measured. By exactly copying a previously established method, conventionalists will be less likely to question the validity of the method, unless they are willing to sacrifice the corresponding historically established experimental results. Once more, we see a returning philosophy in the risk prevention: the contrarian is more likely to escape criticism when using the rules and methods laid out by the conventionalist. Still, the contrarian will need to go beyond a simple copying of accepted methods, by leaving no room for critique. Preferably, each instrument in the satellite should be thoroughly tested beforehand, during and after the measurement. As another highly recommended strategy to prevent criticism or doubts on the methodology, the contrarian would be wise to have all instruments and methods of the satellite mission audited by

independent certified experts trusted by the standard scientific community. If conventionalists still will want to cast doubt over the methodology in that case, they will need to question the serviceability of their expert certification and qualification, which they will not find an attractive option.

When the methodology passes the scrutiny of the conventionalists, the next target will be the validity of the experimental findings. One may argue that unknown factors influenced the results. Alternatively, critics might simply state that more measurements are required to verify the reproducibility of the research. Although this criticism cannot be fully avoided, there are rather simple ways in which it can be minimized. A first option is to perform multiple measurements with the same device, for example, on different days. Additionally, a similar measurement can be performed with multiple identical detectors, to verify that it is at least reproducible by separate instruments. If two detectors use a different technology to measure the same signal, this can give further confidence about its verity. Also for this purpose, auditing the satellite's functionality by independent certified experts trusted by the standard scientific community will aid the contrarian's case. If such experts collaborate with the contrarian during and after the measurements, the legitimacy of the research as perceived by the conventionalist will be further substantiated. Last but not least, a rather low-effort yet effective approach to counter concerns about the reproducibility of the research can be accomplished by following the principles of Open Science. Open Science practices namely aim to address the reproducibility crisis by promoting transparency, collaboration and accountability within the scientific community. By providing full transparency on the research from start till finish, e.g. by publishing intermediate updates on the project in a scientific repository like *Zenodo*, progress can be logged and trust in the project can be strengthened. The present white paper aims to initiate this practice.

Finally, when the methodology and the research results have both passed the conventionalists' scrutiny, the last possible target will be the interpretation of the results. If the results can be interpreted in multiple ways, this will leave room for the conventionalist to reject or dispute the interpretation proposed by the contrarian. For instance, if the satellite measures a declining amplitude of a signal at a specific frequency while it rises in the upper atmosphere of the Earth, the contrarian will interpret this as a weakening of the CMB monopole due to the increasing distance relative to the Earth. In contrast, conventionalists may conjecture that this is due to some charging effect in the detector or another influence that was not checked beforehand. If the satellite is positioned at the second Lagrange point L2 and fails to detect the CMB monopole signal, this may be understood by the contrarian as a confirmation that the signal originates from Earth, but the conventionalist may object by claiming that the detector is simply defective. Such counterarguments will, however, become harder to support if a clear pattern can be observed in when the signal is or is not measured, and when it increases or decreases. If the detector is sensitive to the orientation of the satellite relative to the signal source in a known manner, measuring a pattern as a function of the orientation may provide more conclusive evidence on the location of the signal source, e.g. by making the satellite spin around a well-chosen axis. If signals are measured at different frequencies that confirm unambiguously the blackbody nature of the radiation, conventionalists will also have a harder time rejecting it as an artefact. The Banger satellite team is thus strongly advised to design the mission in such a way that it leaves no room for alternative interpretations.

While a detailed technical analysis of the possibilities lies outside the scope of the present document, I nonetheless would like to draw attention to some highly crucial technological aspects. From Robitaille's radiological analysis of the COBE satellite [9], we learn that the FIRAS device might have measured a microwave signal originating from Earth due to diffraction or leakage of the signal, despite the detector being oriented away from the Earth's surface. However, there is insufficient data available to know what exactly caused the measurement of the signal, if it indeed originated from Earth. If diffraction of the signal around the heat shield was responsible for its detection, a similar mechanism can be assumed for

the Banger satellite, therefore suggesting that its detector can also be directed away from the Earth. Note that, according to Robitaille's microwave diffraction hypothesis, COBE's heat shield would have functioned as an effective fixed low-pass filter for the FIRAS detector.

From my personal communication with Robitaille, I have learned that he does not believe it is possible to measure the CMB monopole signal by aiming a detector toward the Earth, because this would expose the detector to both the microwave radiation and an intense thermal infrared (IR) spectrum, where the latter would oversaturate the detector and correspondingly prevent the unambiguous detection of the microwave radiation. Still, if a detector can be developed with a filtering system that effectively blocks or excludes the thermal radiation from the measurement while letting the microwaves through without altering or contaminating them, orienting it toward the Earth would become a very attractive option, especially if the measured signal can be compared with one recorded when the detector is oriented away from the Earth. Such experiment could even be useful for a single frequency, with a focus on the amplitude of the signal as a function of the orientation and location of the satellite relative to the Earth. I therefore invite everyone of the Banger satellite team to reconsider whether such filtering technology lies within the possibilities of the budget. A feasible technology could, for instance, consist of a low-pass waveguide filter that effectively transports microwaves with geometrical features and walls that reflect infrared radiation, e.g. by means of Bragg reflectors of well-chosen dimensions [65–67]. Frequency-selective surfaces serve as an attractive and complementary alternative [68–70]. Further inspiration can be found in the vast literature on microwave photonics [71–73].

Table II provides an overview of some important satellite parameters of which the variation can reveal useful information about the origin of the CMB monopole. As just discussed, a detector orientation towards the Earth will only be a feasible option if the thermal and optical radiation coming from the Earth will not interfere with the microwave radiation measurement. Once a detector with an effective IR and optical filter is realized, such measurement is expected to reveal crucial information about the CMB monopole origin. Robitaille suspects, for instance, that the CMB monopole originates from the hydrogen bonding network in the oceans nearby the limb of the Earth, where emission from the hydroxyl bonding network drops to zero [5]. In contrast, a detector aimed at nadir may be exposed to mixed microwave radiation from the hydrogen and hydroxyl bonding networks, based on the simulation results by Ulaby et al. [74]. According to this theory, the hydroxyl bonds at nadir would radiate microwaves with a brightness temperature of about two orders of magnitude higher than the hydrogen bonds, making the CMB monopole unidentifiable at this orientation. However, this should be considered speculative due to the theoretical nature of the research by Ulaby et al. The validity of this theory can only be tested by means of dedicated experiments. Until reliable comprehensive empirical data is obtained on this topic, the opposing possibility of the hydroxyl bonding network being completely microwave silent over all emission angles, for example, cannot be excluded. This makes a satellite mission with the purpose to study the angular dependence of the oceans' microwave emission spectrum highly recommended in this context. Still, such a mission, if technologically achievable, may be considered more challenging than one in which the detector is kept oriented away from the Earth. The technical restraints within the satellite budget will thus determine whether this ambition is feasible within a first mission, or should be kept for a later one.

Table II. Satellite parameters and how they are predicted to affect the measured CMB monopole signal according to the scientific consensus and according to Robitaille’s paradigm.

Satellite parameter	Predicted effect on measured CMB monopole signal	
	<i>According to scientific consensus</i>	<i>According to Robitaillean paradigm</i>
Detector orientation toward Earth with ideal IR/optical filter	Weak to non-existent backscattered CMB monopole signal mixed with strong microwave radiation emitted from Earth	CMB monopole signal possibly mixed with strong microwave radiation emitted from hydroxyl bonding network of the oceans, except nearby the Earth’s limb
Detector orientation away from Earth	Isotropic CMB monopole signal	CMB monopole signal amplitude depends on diffraction or leakage into detector
Distance relative to Earth surface	Constant signal amplitude outside the atmosphere	Signal amplitude decreasing with increasing distance
Location over the Earth surface	Constant signal amplitude	Possibly fluctuating signal amplitude due to dry areas at Earth’s limb
Detector screen position	Signal can be blocked or affected when a screen is placed between detector and outer space, i.e. above the detector	Signal can be blocked or affected when a screen is placed between satellite and Earth’s atmosphere, i.e. below or at the sides of the satellite

For a detector oriented away from the Earth, varying its orientation can reveal an interesting pattern in the recorded signal, but any associated reorientation of other components of the satellite, such as the heat shield, may complicate the interpretation of the results. Conventionalists may, for instance, speculate based on the satellite geometry that differences in the infrared and optical shielding or microwave reflections are responsible for a varying signal, rather than the orientation relative to an assumed Earthly microwave source. Still, the simultaneous measurement at different orientations by otherwise identical detectors may reveal relationships between the measured signals that conventionalists cannot easily explain away. Spinning such a satellite around a well-chosen axis would provide additional information on the relationships.

For a fixed detector orientation away from the Earth, the distance of the satellite relative to the Earth surface is a particularly interesting controllable parameter, because Robitaille predicts a decreasing CMB monopole amplitude as a function of it both within and outside the atmosphere, whereas this would be hard to explain in the standard theory. At a fixed distance from the Earth’s surface, any strong variation of the recorded signal as a function of the location relative to the oceans versus the continents will also be problematic for the standard theory. However, the Robitaillean paradigm does not guarantee such variation to occur, because the angular relationship as well as the detailed atmospheric transport mechanisms of microwaves emitted by the oceans are still insufficiently understood. In this regard, it is interesting to note that the current plan of the Banger satellite team is to place the device in geostationary orbit, i.e. 36,000 km above the equator, as opposed to the 900 km altitude in polar orbit of COBE. While the measurement in geostationary orbit has the advantage of providing a stable location relative to the

Earth surface, measuring the variation in signal during its ascent toward that location will especially be informative.

For a fixed satellite orientation and location relative to the Earth, Robitaille's theory does not predict any variation of the measured CMB monopole signal, unless something changes in the radiation transport around the satellite or into the detector. This insight opens the door to several other possibilities in the satellite design. Figure 1 depicts three main options. Adding above the detector a removable screen that reflects microwaves from outer space provides an alternative way to check the origin of the measured radiation. If the screen is designed such that microwaves from outer space cannot enter the detector while microwaves originating from Earth are amplified into the detector by more efficient diffraction and reflection, comparing the measurements with and without the screen may provide conclusive evidence for the research question, if emission by the screen into the detector can be avoided. Similarly, microwaves coming from Earth can be blocked from entering the detector by placing a removable screen underneath or around the satellite. As should be noted, the screen can severely interfere with the beam pattern of the antenna. Moreover, microwaves easily diffract, so achieving the desired directionality forms a significant challenge on its own.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the satellite (in black) with the addition of one or more removable or fixed screens (in grey), with (a) a removable screen above the detector to avoid radiation from outer space from entering it, (b) a removable screen underneath and around the detector to prevent radiation from Earth from entering it, and (c) a combination of these two options with fixed screens for two separate detectors. The ticks on the screen represent surface structures to prevent diffraction at the corresponding screen side.

If a static satellite design is preferred, an alternative option is to use two detectors that simultaneously perform the measurement, one of which only receives microwaves from the Earth through diffraction and reflection, and the other of which only receives microwaves from outer space. Instead of a removable screen, this permits alternative filters, such as specially designed edges and surfaces to prevent diffraction. Yet another option is to use multiple antennas with differing filters, geometry or surface features to distinguish between diffracted and directly incident microwave radiation. However, in such static cases, it is recommended to add a microwave source on different sides of the satellite, so switching it on and off can confirm that each detector is working well, if natural microwaves are absent from each direction of interest. The possible usage of polarization filters also deserves a special mentioning here, because microwaves typically get polarized during diffraction around edges.

Still, as a general rule of thumb, the more complex the satellite design and the measurement procedure, the higher the chance on failure. In this regard, optimizing the satellite mission requires weighing the technological risks against the scientific-philosophical ones. In other words, a compromise will need to be made between a sufficiently straightforward design with a low chance on technical failure, and a sufficiently informative experiment with a high level of conclusiveness. Since a more in-depth

discussion of the technological aspects lies outside the scope of the present white paper, I will leave this consideration for future discussions.

In a nutshell, I proposed several ways to mitigate the six main risks regarding the convincingness and impact of the Banger satellite mission, which can be generalized to all experimental research that contradicts or aims to contradict the scientific consensus. Next to the three generic risks of neglect by the scientific community, distractive counterarguments and misinterpretations, I paid special attention to the three more targeted risks of criticism on the methodology, on the results and on the interpretation of the satellite research. Returning themes in the solutions are to use popular and established traditions and methodology, to keep the message focused, to invite independent certified experts to audit the work, to follow Open Science practices, and to leave no room for interpretation of the experimental results with respect to the hypothesis to be tested. Regarding the latter, several suggestions were given on how to produce conclusive findings, where reproducibility of the measurements and a clear pattern in them may be understood as two of the most important aspects. Still, an important question we did not yet address is whether a satellite is the only option to experimentally test the core hypothesis of Robitaille's work on the CMB in a conclusive and convincing manner. In Section 3.2, I will argue that it is not, even though a satellite mission deserves a higher priority.

3.2. Is a satellite the only option? – Revenge of the ROT

A satellite mission has a few advantages over ground-based experimental research for the determination of the CMB monopole origin. Firstly, far above the lower layers of the atmosphere, Rayleigh and Mie scattering of microwave radiation do no longer take place, which makes it possible to empirically determine the direction from which the radiation originates. The lack of scattering also prevents the radiation spectrum from potentially being distorted while traveling through free space, providing direct access to its blackbody nature. The relatively large distance from the Earth surface moreover reduces the possible interference of artificially generated electromagnetic radiation. The stronger vacuum conditions for satellites also prevent the interference of water condensation in the detector, unlike for antennas on Earth, as well as airplane, rocket, and balloon experiments [9]. Next to these experimental upsides, a satellite is more likely to turn heads in comparison to a ground-based instrument. There are, however, some disadvantages to a satellite mission as well, such as its greater complexity, technical limitations, relatively high cost and the significantly lower flexibility in repairing or adapting the instruments during research. If the main purpose of the investigation is to determine the true origin of the CMB, it does make sense to consider more down-to-Earth experimental settings too.

The measurements performed with the ROT-54/2.6 antenna with respect to the CMB serve as a helpful reference, because Herouni clearly considered them as conclusive evidence for the absence of the CMB signal. Yet, they failed to draw much – if any – attention from the standard scientific community. An interesting question to ask ourselves is therefore whether Herouni's findings and interpretation should be branded as unconvincing from the perspective of the conventional astrophysicists. The answer to this question is not straightforward, because we lack direct feedback from the broader scientific community. Note here the difference between conclusiveness and convincingness, where the former stands for the decisiveness of the argument, whereas the latter refers to its effect on the belief of Big Bang proponents. This is not simply a matter of being right or wrong. It is a matter of changing people's minds.

For as far as I can base myself on my personal interactions with other researchers on this topic, I highly doubt that the broader scientific community would easily be convinced by Herouni's work about the absence of the CMB monopole signal, if it would be made more aware of it. Questioning the cosmic

nature of the CMB is highly controversial even in non-standard cosmology, as illustrated by the reactions on my presentation at DemystiCon 2025 [41]. Why would it be any less controversial for standard cosmologists? Even though standard cosmologists seem little moved by the lack of evidence for the cosmic nature of the CMB, as pointed out by Robitaille, we may expect them to request extraordinary evidence for the claim of an Earthly origin. These cognitive biases amplify the Semmelweis reflex, i.e. the natural tendency of the scientific community to dismiss evidence that challenges the scientific consensus [75, 76]. Once again, contrarians are advised to assume a worst-case scenario, where conventionalists will try every trick in the book to counter or discredit controversial experimental findings.

As such, is it possible to obtain a both conclusive and convincing argument against the Big Bang theory by means of a ground-based experimental study like Herouni's? I want to argue that this is indeed possible, and even realistic, at least in principle, but that it is also more complicated and prone to failure than a satellite mission. Firstly, while a satellite mission may seem technologically more challenging, performing measurements within the lower atmosphere has its own limitations. Atmospheric interference, ground pickup and other possible environmental factors like birds, for instance, strongly complicate ground-based measurements. Secondly, the measurement results are more open for interpretation due to the overall uncertain and convoluted contribution of these factors. Returning to Table I, this forms an inherently bigger risk of criticism on the interpretation of the experimental data. Thirdly, to minimize this risk of multi-interpretability, a sufficiently large body of experimental data will need to be collected to substantiate any patterns in them. More specifically, the patterns need to be clear enough to undeniably contradict a cosmic origin of the CMB monopole, while supporting atmospheric radiation transport profiles that align with an Earthly origin. Fourthly, although we can currently speculate about these patterns based on Robitaille's suggestions on the atmospheric microwave radiation transport mechanisms, quite some uncertainty remains about them and alternative mechanisms are hard to exclude. The design of dedicated ground-based experiments will inevitably be limited by these uncertainties. Because such experiments can provide valuable information on the underlying atmospheric microwave transport, they may benefit more from a trial-and-error strategy as compared to a satellite mission, making them eventually costlier in time, effort and financial means.

For all of these reasons, a satellite mission should be prioritized over any ground-based experiments for the purpose of obtaining conclusive and convincing experimental evidence against the Big Bang theory and in favor of the core hypothesis of Robitaille's message regarding the CMB, as formulated in Section 1.2. Nonetheless, ground-based empirical research becomes particularly interesting for the purpose of testing what I consider the secondary hypothesis of Robitaille's theory on the CMB:

The monopole of the CMB originates from the oceans on Earth.

As discussed in Section 3.1, a satellite can only reliably indicate which Earthly source would emit the CMB monopole, if its detector is oriented toward the Earth surface, which requires an effective IR and optical filter for meaningful measurements. This is technologically challenging on its own, implying a higher risk of failure relative to a satellite detector oriented away from the Earth to test only the core hypothesis. Even if such challenging satellite mission is successful, it will only provide limited information about the Earthly microwave source and especially the corresponding radiation transport profiles within the lower layers of the atmosphere. Insight into the latter is essential to obtain a more reliable and substantiated explanation for historic ground-based observations, in terms of how microwaves emitted by the oceans would have arrived at the location of measurement and would have been recorded by the detector in question.

For example, as I have learned from personal communication with Robitaille, he suspects that Herouni was not able to measure the CMB monopole primarily due to the unique structure of the ROT-54/2.6. According to him, the key feature that set Herouni's antenna apart from other ground-based detectors was its edgeless design that prevented diffraction into the receiver. This argument is based on the assumption that any CMB monopole radiation arriving at the antenna was incident under small angles with the Earth surface, after having been emitted from the oceans under similar small angles and having been scattered in the lower layers of the atmosphere due to Mie scattering. According to Robitaille, the antenna's location in a dry region, remote from extended bodies of water, would thus only have been of secondary importance. This explanation, however, heavily relies on theory and assumptions that remain unverified for now and should therefore be considered speculative. Moreover, it does not provide any quantitative information on the microwave radiation transport, such as how much scattering occurs and how strongly the intensity of the CMB monopole signal varies as a function of the distance to the ocean. Even if a quantitative model is built to quantify the scattering coefficient and radiation intensity variation, it would on its turn be based on untested assumptions. Without additional ground-based experiments, these uncertainties and gaps in knowledge cannot be overcome. Similar remarks can be given about the reinterpretation of any other historic measurements related to the CMB monopole within the Robitaillean paradigm.

Hence, whereas a satellite mission should remain the primary choice for testing Robitaille's core hypothesis of an Earthly CMB monopole, ground-based experiments can play an auxiliary role. In particular, they can be performed to test the secondary hypothesis of the oceanic origin, as well as to substantiate and quantify the CMB monopole radiation transport throughout the atmosphere. Correspondingly, proponents of the Robitaillean paradigm may envision an experimental strategy in which satellite missions are prioritized in a first stage to effectively destabilize or disprove the Big Bang theory, followed by a second stage with ground-based measurements to further substantiate Robitaille's assumptions on the atmospheric CMB radiation transport. Still, with the Big Bang theory and Λ CDM model as strongly embedded in the scientific consensus as they are today, it is hard to predict at which stage the broader astrophysical community will change course based on the accumulating counterevidence. As the history of the Semmelweis reflex suggests [75, 76], it may easily take decades for the scientific community to recognize the importance of a controversial experiment. For this reason, it is once more justified to assume a worst-case scenario for contrarians wanting to test Robitaille's hypotheses with a ground-based approach, where the broader scientific community will still uphold the Big Bang theory and defend it at all costs against the already available empirical data challenging it.

Returning to Table I, this requires preventing criticism on the methodology, results and interpretation of the ground-based experiments. For the methodology, an elegant option could be to replicate Pensias and Wilson's horn antenna, place it in a dry region on Earth and try to reproduce Herouni's findings. Still, using the same experimental principles in a cheaper setup could be sufficient to engage a larger portion of the scientific community in a constructive dialogue, because this is considered a standard technology to measure the CMB. In this regard, Herouni namely faced an additional obstacle for otherwise similar experimental findings, due to the unique design of his antenna, as illustrated by the Arutyunyan's and Khachatryan's criticism discussed in Section 2.1. By instead using a standard method that led to Pensias and Wilson's Nobel Prize in Physics, conventionalists will have a harder time countering or questioning the methodology. For the contrarian, it further provides a straightforward argument why this Nobel Prize should be put into question, if the standard method indeed reveals the absence of the CMB monopole.

Note, however, that this strategy assumes the absence of the CMB monopole radiation at the location of Herouni's telescope, in contrast with Robitaille's perspective that ROT-54/2.6's design was mainly responsible for the lack of the radiation signal in Herouni's measurements. If the radiation is instead

present at the location, but arriving at small angles with the Earth surface, in line with Robitaille's interpretation, a classical horn antenna will likely be insufficient to avoid measuring the radiation at specific angles, due to diffraction of the microwaves around the horn. We therefore need to distinguish two decisive possibilities in the contrarian ground-based experiment:

1. either the budget and technological constraints allow developing an antenna with a sufficiently high angular resolution to prevent or severely suppress diffraction at specific orientations, and with a sufficiently standardized design to avoid criticism on the methodology,
2. or no such resolution can be obtained with standardized techniques within the budget.

In the first case, it should be possible to measure the absence or suppression of the CMB monopole signal at the orientations where neither direct incidence of the radiation, nor strong diffraction of it into the detector occurs. A comprehensive measurement as a function of the detector orientation may then provide a conclusive argument against the cosmic origin of the CMB monopole. If the anisotropy of the signal can be linked to the nearest ocean border, this will add further weight to the argument. Still, caution is required, in order to eliminate all options for conventionalists to interpret the results in favor of the Big Bang theory. In the second case, it may be hard – if not impossible – to find locations on Earth where the absence of the CMB monopole signal can be demonstrated with a standard antenna. The low angular resolution of the antenna will then prevent identifying the anisotropy of the measured radiation in a conclusive manner. Conventionalists can then easily keep defending their claim of an isotropic signal as observed from the Earth. The Big Bang theory can then only be challenged with the measurements, if the recorded signal intensity is unambiguously lower than the expected brightness temperature of 2.7 K would permit.

Unfortunately, this severely complicates a planning of the ground-based experiments due to the uncertain microwave radiation transport from the oceans to locations at land. If the CMB monopole radiation profile in the atmosphere were accurately understood, the selection of a feasible location for the detector to test Robitaille's theory would be more straightforward. Currently, it is even unclear whether the CMB monopole signal is effectively absent or significantly faint at one or more locations on Earth with dry and cold weather conditions to enable stable measurements. If no such locations exist, antennas with a low angular resolution will have little use to test Robitaille's theory. Detectors with a high angular resolution could then form a solution, but also for their envisioned measurements, several uncertainties remain, especially with regard to how convincing a recorded anisotropic signal will be to conventionalists. This makes the ground-based approach inherently more prone to failure from a scientific-philosophical viewpoint.

Nonetheless, this does not make dedicated Earthly measurements useless or unnecessary. At the very least, they will provide more clarity on the atmospheric CMB monopole radiation transport with respect to its suspected oceanic origin. For this purpose, the signal's anisotropy and intensity need to be investigated as a function of the location on Earth. Next to that, using traditional antenna designs can provide a more profound understanding of their limitations with respect to diffraction of the microwave radiation. As should be noted, Robitaille indeed suspects that Herouni's antenna is unique in its ability to avoid diffraction in the detector, in comparison to all other historic devices that measured the CMB monopole from the ground. Experimentally demonstrating this limitation of the historic instruments by creating a copy and testing it can therefore be an effective strategy to debase the conventionalists' claim that cosmic radiation was observed, even if measuring the absence of the signal is not possible with these reconstructed devices.

If, on the other hand, such standard detectors can avoid diffraction with or without minor adaptations, or if locations can be found where they measure the absence or severe suppression of the CMB monopole, they will form an attractive avenue for the contrarian to disprove the Big Bang theory. Preferably, Herouni’s results should then be reproduced with various standard detector types simultaneously. This might be even possible with a relatively low budget. Table III presents the current price estimations given by the Large Language Model (LLM) Gemini 3. For an unambiguous measurement of the CMB, cryogenic cooling is a strong requirement to sufficiently reduce the signal-to-noise ratio for any detector type. Adding high-electron-mobility transistors (HEMTs) for ultra-low-noise amplification of the radio wave is a second strong recommendation in modern setups. The combination of both are the primary price drivers for the cheaper antenna technologies (satellite dishes and horn antennas with a Dicke radiometer), whereas cryogenic cooling to sub-Kelvin temperatures is the dominant factor for the more expensive detector types. Within a budget of 100k USD, a satellite dish with a software-defined radio (SDR) and a horn antenna with a Dicke radiometer, both using cryogenics and HEMTs, can be combined in the same study. Applying the same cooling system to the two detectors may even compress the pricing further.

Table III. Detector technologies with or without cryogenic cooling and/or high-electron-mobility transistors (HEMTs), the estimated price for a complete system, and their feasibility for an unambiguous measurement of the CMB or its absence in a ground-based experiment, as suggested by Gemini 3.

Detector type	Cryo	HEMTs	Estimated price (USD)*	Feasibility
Software-defined radio (SDR) & satellite dish	no	no	150 – 350	Nearly impossible
	no	yes	400 – 800	Very low
	yes	no	1,500 – 4,000	Low
	yes	yes	5,000 – 15,000+	Moderate to high
Horn antenna & Dicke radiometer	no	no	500 – 2,500	Impossible
	no	yes	2,500 – 10,000	Very low
	yes	no	15,000 – 40,000	Possible, but hard
	yes	yes	60,000 – 150,000+	Very high
Neutron transmutation doped germanium (NTD Ge) bolometers	yes	yes	150,000 – 400,000+	Very high
Microwave kinetic inductance detectors (MKIDs)	yes	yes	250,000 – 600,000+	Moderate to high, but complex
Hot electron bolometers (HEB)	yes	yes	400,000 – 800,000+	Moderate to high
Transition edge sensors (TES)	yes	yes	500,000 – 1,200,000+	High, but complex

*Prices are indicative only. Different prompts led to different price estimations by Gemini 3, but the order of magnitude remained the same.

A neutron transmutation doped germanium (NTD Ge) bolometer forms another recommended option, but this will push the required budget significantly higher due to the sub-Kelvin cooling necessary for unambiguous CMB absence detection. Microwave kinetic inductance detectors (MKIDs) can in principle be used for absolute measurements, but they are technically complex to calibrate, as they are more suitable for differential anisotropy mapping. Transition edge sensors (TES) are also usually applied for anisotropy mapping. They require expensive dilution refrigerators for an unambiguous absolute measurement and their cost is further driven by their superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) multiplexing readout systems. Finally, hot electron bolometers need a complex and expensive infrastructure and would be overkill to check the presence of the CMB in a ground-based detector, because they are more suitable for spectral analysis.

To better understand the price estimations by Gemini 3, Table IV provides an overview of the estimated minimal costs for the corresponding cryogenic cooling techniques. For the satellite dish with SDR and HEMTs, the LLM assumed a liquid nitrogen (LN₂) cooling system, which explains its relatively low cost. However, this implies a cooling temperature of 77 K, associated with significant thermal self-noise from the detector. Under these conditions, the CMB could still be detected by intensive statistical averaging with the SDR, but this severely hampers the unambiguity of the experiment. To convince conventionalists, this procedure will likely be insufficient, so a cooling goal of around 4 K seems to be the recommended maximum. This forms a second argument to consider a shared 4 K cooling system for a satellite dish with a SDR and a horn antenna with a Dicke radiometer in the same study.

As should be emphasized once again, an interesting site to place such detectors would be in the proximity of the ROT-54/2.6 antenna in Armenia, because this allows comparing the measurements with Herouni's for the same location. If the new detectors also reveal the absence of the CMB signal, this can be understood as a direct confirmation of Herouni's findings with more standardized technology. If, in contrast, a CMB signal can be detected with the new detectors at the ROT-54/2.6 antenna site, this would contradict Herouni's conclusions, while supporting Robitaille's interpretation, motivating a further investigation into the difference between the antennas. Performing the experiment elsewhere is more subject to speculation, because the microwave scattering mechanisms in the atmosphere as proposed by Robitaille [3, 7] are still insufficiently understood. More precisely, the effective scattering coefficient is currently unknown, so it is unclear at which minimal distance from extended water bodies in combination with which altitudes the CMB monopole signal would disappear, if such effect occurs on Earth. Of course, choosing a location that is located further from any oceans, lakes or other water bodies than the Herouni telescope site is a rather safe alternative, but it is anyhow more disputable than the ROT-54/2.6 site due to the lack of any preceding collocal measurements.

Once criticism on the methodology is prevented by using conventional instruments and criticism on the research findings is minimized by reproducing the results with multiple detector types and Open Science principles, there is still the hurdle of multi-interpretability to tackle. If the results are limited to measurements in which the CMB signal cannot be found at a specific location, as in the example of Herouni's measurements, proponents of the Big Bang theory may still resort to questioning the validity of the conclusion that the CMB would not come from outer space. As a possible counterargument, the CMB could still be present at the detector's location, but the instrument was not able to record it due to unknown or speculative factors. Alternatively, the CMB could be absent at that location for unknown or speculative reasons that do not contradict its presumed cosmic origin and presence. Even though such speculations may seem hard to defend from the perspective of the contrarian, they may suffice for most conventionalists to classify the experiment as an odd outlier providing food for thought, rather than a decisive finding disproving their long-held worldview.

Table IV. Cryogenic technologies, their cooling temperature goal, the main constituents of the total cooling system contributing to their price, and the estimated minimum price range for a complete cooling system, as suggested by Gemini 3.

Cryogenic technology	Cooling goal	Main Constituents	Estimated price (USD)*
Liquid nitrogen (LN2) system	77 K	Vacuum vessel, radiation shielding, LN2	5,000 – 15,000
Gifford-McMahon (GM) cooler	40 K	GM cryocooler, compressor, vacuum vessel, copper thermal links	25,000 – 40,000
Pulse tube (PT) cooler	4 K	Two-stage PT cooler, high-power compressor, remote valve motor	50,000 – 80,000
Liquid helium (LHe) system	4 K	Vacuum vessel, radiation shielding, ⁴ He gas	50,000 – 85,000
Lambda Point Refrigerator (LPR)	1.8 – 2.1 K	Custom heat exchangers, vacuum pump, capillary lines, LHe base system	65,000 – 115,000
⁴ He sorption cooler	1 K	Charcoal pot, ⁴ He sorption pump, heat switches, 4 K pre-stage	80,000 – 120,000
³ He sorption cooler	250 mK	Ultra-high vacuum, ³ He gas, sorption pumps, 4 K pre-stage	120,000 – 180,000
Adiabatic demagnetization refrigerator (ADR)	100 mK	Superconducting magnet, paramagnetic salt pill, 4 K pre-stage	200,000 – 350,000
Dilution refrigerator (DR)	< 50 mK	Mixing chamber, ³ He/ ⁴ He mixture, 4 K pre-stage, pumps, compressors	450,000 – 700,000

*Prices are indicative only. Different prompts led to different price estimations by Gemini 3, but the order of magnitude remained the same. These prices are for the cryogenic hardware only. They do not include the vacuum vessel, custom internal thermal strapping, thermometers, or the detectors. Also, He gas prices are volatile and can add tens of thousands of dollars to the cost of a dilution or sorption system.

I see a way in which such an impasse can be avoided, by focusing on reproducible patterns. By making the detector mobile, it can perform measurements in dry areas as well as near lakes, oceans or other

extended water bodies. If successive measurements repeatably reveal the presence of the CMB signal near the water bodies and its absence or severe suppression at several dry sites, this pattern will become hard to deny by conventionalists. That is, the detector's ability to detect the CMB monopole signal at certain locations would reveal that it works as expected, preventing further speculation on its functionality. Additionally, the signal's absence or faintness in the measurements at multiple dry sites would defy the odd outlier argument, because the presumed outliers start forming a pattern. Similarly, if the signal's anisotropy can be repeatably linked to the presence of nearby extended water bodies, conventionalists will have a hard time denying the pattern.

A mobile detector setup may moreover reveal intermediate situations at locations where one or more water bodies are still close enough for their emitted microwave spectrum to reach the device, while far enough to have it measurably weakened in comparison to more water-rich locations. In line with the proposed atmospheric microwave scattering mechanisms in the Robitaille paradigm, the CMB signal at such a location is accordingly expected to have a lower amplitude, and possibly a noticeable anisotropy as well with a maximal amplitude in the direction of the water. If the error on the temperature measurement is sufficiently low and the detector can record the signal at multiple frequencies, it will even be possible to study the signal amplitude reduction as a function of the frequency. Next to that, if the extent of CMB monopole scattering in the atmosphere for the measured frequencies is frequency-independent, the reduction factor of the signal amplitude at an intermediate location will be constant for the different frequencies, which implies a variable apparent brightness temperature as a function of the frequency (except in the Rayleigh-Jeans limit). If the scattering is frequency-dependent, the measured temperatures may be even stronger dependent on the frequency. Such a dependence cannot be explained in a straightforward manner in the standard paradigm. Moreover, measurements at intermediate locations could give valuable information about the effective scattering coefficient of the atmosphere for the CMB monopole, providing a more detailed insight into the blackbody microwave radiation transport mechanisms in the atmosphere. A major challenge will be to accurately account for any atmospheric emission at the selected detector frequencies, e.g. due to the presence of aqueous aerosols. Still, the more locations are used for measurements with a mobile detector, especially at varying altitudes, the more clarity can be obtained on the role of the atmospheric emission.

I did not cover balloon and rocket experiments in detail in the present section, because these platforms are more comparable to a satellite, in the sense that they allow similar parameters as presented in Table II, yet sharing some issues with the ground-based alternatives, such as the problem of water condensation. I want to invite proponents of the Robitaille paradigm to explore these directions as complementary approaches to satellite and ground-based projects. Anyhow, with the recent advances and commercialization of rocket transport and satellite technology, the latter has become a competitive option. Another reason to classify balloon and rocket experiments in a similar group as satellites relates to the minimized atmospheric interference at higher altitude. Still, balloons and rockets deserve their own category, because they allow to investigate the CMB monopole signal properties as a function of the altitude within the denser parts of the atmosphere, which is not possible with satellites. Similar to ground-based measurements with a mobile detector, such investigations can further advance our understanding of the CMB radiation transport within the atmosphere.

In summary, a satellite is not necessarily the only option to convincingly test the conventional and the Robitaille theories on the CMB monopole origin, but ground-based measurements are less straightforward, and should therefore be given a lower priority. In my estimation, Herouni's findings are likely insufficiently convincing to the broader scientific community due to the unique design of the ROT-54/2.6 antenna. By using one or more standardized detectors with a conventional methodology, including external auditing and Open Science practices, a measured absence or strong suppression of

the CMB monopole signal will become more convincing to conventionalists, although it remains unclear for now whether such measurement is possible with sufficiently standardized technology. Alternatively, reconstructing and testing historic instruments may reveal their limitations in terms of microwave diffraction into the detector, debasing the conventional narrative of the cosmic origin of the measured signal. Still, the highest impact may be expected when experiments reveal a clear pattern between when the CMB monopole signal is detected and when it is not or at a significantly weaker intensity with the same instrument. This can be most easily realized by making the detector mobile, so measurements at different locations can be compared in a straightforward manner. Next to revealing the true origin of the CMB monopole, measurements at different locations in the atmosphere, whether ground-, balloon-, or rocket-based, will provide valuable new insights into the underlying atmospheric microwave radiation transport mechanisms. A similar conclusion can be made about documenting any anisotropy as a function of the location with a mobile detector.

4. Conclusion

In the present white paper, I proposed Robitaille's core hypothesis regarding the Earthly origin of the CMB monopole as the most suitable starting point to introduce his work into the academic discussion. This choice is based on its ability to be experimentally tested with a satellite, as well as the importance of the CMB monopole for cosmology and astrophysics. However, a successful satellite mission indicating an Earthly origin of the CMB monopole does not guarantee a high impact on the cosmological dialogue held in academia. Conventionalists are namely trained and incentivized to employ various defense mechanisms to protect the scientific consensus, including the standard cosmological model, from any harm. Examples can be found in the dialogue – or better the lack thereof – on Herouni's measurements that point towards the absence of the CMB at the location of his ROT-54/2.6 antenna. In as far as counterarguments have been found on Herouni's dismissal of the Big Bang theory, they either were based on misconceptions and publication-technical features of the work, or they put the correct functioning of the telescope into question, ignoring other successful measurements with the device. Apart from that, an assessment of Herouni's work on the CMB seems to be lacking in the international academic literature.

Based on these examples and my own estimations, I classified the anticipated defense mechanisms of conventionalists against any experimental challenge to the scientific consensus into six categories: (i) ignoring the challenge, (ii) distractive counterarguments, (iii) misinterpretations, (iv) criticism on the methodology, (v) criticism on the experimental results, and (vi) criticism on the interpretation. When successful, any of these mechanisms can prevent the experimental research from being taken seriously by the standard scientific community. Accordingly, I proposed several strategies for contrarian experimentalists to prevent or mitigate these risks, for each of the categories, including (i) directly engaging in communication with the broader scientific community, (ii) keeping the message singular and focused, and refocusing the conversation when necessary, (iii) screening communication for clarity, (iv) using standard methods audited by independent certified experts, (v) repeating the measurements and using Open Science principles, and (vi) leaving no room for alternative interpretations. Applying the latter point to a satellite mission investigating the origin of the CMB monopole, one of the most promising approaches is to reproducibly vary the instrument's distance relative to the Earth surface and measure the change in CMB monopole signal intensity. Another option is to add movable screens on the satellite to reversibly block possible microwave radiation from entering the detector from suspected directions. As a more technologically challenging recourse, developing a detector with an effective IR

and optical filter combined with a sufficiently high angular resolution would allow scanning the microwave emission from the Earth surface and thus also the oceans directly, which would likely provide very valuable data with respect to the research question.

Besides a satellite, additional ground-based measurements of the CMB monopole are also possible to investigate its origin. Despite the more limited frequency range and other atmospheric interference issues in comparison to the satellite case, this approach is obviously more practical in terms of instrument adaptation and repair. As a particular advantage, the distance and altitude relative to oceans or other extended water bodies can be regulated by making the detector mobile. Performing and comparing such measurements at various sites on Earth with the same device has the potential to reveal a reproducible and eventually predictable pattern, indicating not only whether the CMB monopole has an Earthly origin, but also whether it indeed comes from the oceans, as suggested by Robitaille. It moreover permits to empirically estimate the effective scattering coefficient and radiation transport profiles of the CMB monopole in the lower atmosphere as a function of location. This can as well provide a deeper insight into previous Earth-based measurements and their quantitative reinterpretation according to Robitaille's theory. Still, ground-based experiments have several serious disadvantages in comparison to satellites, such as atmospheric interference, ground pickup, and other environmental factors, a higher risk of multi-interpretability, the need for more data to be collected in order to obtain a sufficient conclusiveness, and the remaining uncertainty about atmospheric microwave radiation transport mechanisms. For these reasons, a satellite mission deserves a higher priority for the purpose of testing the Earthly origin of the CMB monopole. Ground-based measurements instead can play a complementary secondary role, to gain a more profound understanding of historic experiments and the atmospheric CMB monopole radiation transport.

Author contributions

P. Vanraes conceived the scientific-philosophical risk analysis research idea and methodology, performed the literature study, created the figure and tables, and wrote and reviewed the text.

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The author declares that he has no competing financial interests. P. Vanraes knows Pierre-Marie Robitaille in person, considers him a friend, and is a proponent of the Robitaillean paradigm.

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Data Availability

The data generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding authors on reasonable request.

Additional information

This document is not accompanied with supplementary information.

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This version of the white paper has not undergone formal peer review before being published on *Zenodo*. An earlier version of the manuscript was reviewed by Prof. Dr. Pierre-Marie Robitaille, whose feedback was taken into account for the preparation of the current version. Still, the current version presents the perspective of the author only, unless mentioned otherwise. The author does not intend to submit the white paper in its current form for formal peer review, because a suitable journal does not seem to exist for it due to the specialized nature of CMB research on the one hand, and either the conservative bias in formal peer review in astrophysical or cosmological journals or the high publication costs in peer reviewed journals that would otherwise be a feasible outlet on the other hand. Changes in the formal peer review status of the article or an adapted version of it will be communicated on *Zenodo*, either in the metadata or in the article's comment section. The author welcomes feedback on the article, whether through personal contact, open peer review reports or any other form of communication.

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